

The Petit Riad

The Riad is a traditional type of housing that probably first appeared in Marrakech nine centuries ago (in the palace of the Almoravid Ali Ben Youssef (1106-1143)). It was adopted afterwards in other cities such as Fez, Meknes, Rabat, Salé and Tetouan.

The Petit Riad of the Bahia Palace has two large rooms richly decorated with floral, geometric and epigraphic motifs and a tripartite alcove (*Bhu*) which faces a large door giving access to a double oblong room. The whole surrounds an open-air courtyard furnished with a quadripartite garden and centred by a white marble fountain.

On the south side, inscriptions sculpted on plaster put forward the date of 1898 as the date of construction of this pavilion.

This space served as an office for Vizier Ba Hmad and a beautiful welcoming place for his guests of honour.

Under the French protectorate, it continued to play this administrative function by hosting the offices of Marshal Lyautey.